

PROPOSAL OF A FATIGUE CRACK EXTENSION MODE AND ITS PREDICTION METHOD — DAMAGE ACCUMULATION MODE FATIGUE CRACK PROPAGATION

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A novel fatigue crack extension mode, not deformation mode, and methods for predicting fatigue properties in high-strength steels are proposed as the reason why high-strength steels exhibit different fatigue properties from those of conventional steels. An example of a different fatigue property is that the threshold stress intensity factor range of a long crack in high-strength steel is still not as high as expected from the hardness. At present, there is no clear explanation for this reason. Therefore, the material cannot be used with confidence. The authors propose that this is due to a different crack extension mechanism. In other words, the authors propose the existence of a mechanism of fatigue crack extension other than the generally accepted mechanism of fatigue crack extension. Fatigue crack is generally considered to grow due to plastic deformation by alternating slip. Based on the proposed novel mechanism, the mode of fatigue crack extension is called damage accumulation mode fatigue crack propagation. This name differs from the conventional name. The names focus on the loading mode, i.e., Modes I, II, and III. The proposed name focuses on the extension mechanism. The presentation reviews examples of damage accumulation mode fatigue crack propagation in various high-strength steels and presents a method for predicting the propagation behaviour.

Keywords: Metal fatigue, Fatigue crack propagation, Damage accumulation, Fatigue crack extension mode

INTRODUCTION

In general, predicting the fatigue strength of metallic materials often relies on factors such as tensile strength and Vickers hardness (Nishijima [1]). However, certain high-strength steels defy conventional fatigue limit predictions, presenting a significant challenge in strength design. One contributing factor to this anomaly is believed to be the influence of inclusions (Murakami [2]). Experimental analyses of cracked materials have revealed that the threshold stress intensity factor range (ΔK_{th}) for high-strength steels is notably smaller than that observed in general steels (Tanaka [3]). The authors propose that these materials exhibit a distinct fatigue crack propagation mode termed the Damage Accumulation mode (DA mode). Hamada *et al.* [4] have identified at least two fatigue crack propagation modes: the plastic deformation mode (PD mode) and the DA mode. In the PD mode, crack growth occurs through a sequence of opening and closing cycles, induced by

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alternating slip and resultant plastic deformation at the crack tip—attributed to dislocation emission (Neumann [5]). The deformation mode at the crack tip is characterized as Mode I. Conversely, damage accumulation mode fatigue crack propagation results from Mode II deformation at the crack tip. Cyclic shear loading on a material with a microstructure, stemming from processes such as rolling, has been identified as a contributor to damage accumulation, as reported in [4].

In this scenario, fatigue crack propagation ensues as damage accumulates near the crack tip due to cyclic loading. This leads to the growth of voids that evolve into subcracks, subsequently coalescing with the primary crack and propagates. A model outlining crack propagation through the iterative occurrence of these processes has been postulated. For instance, fatigue crack growth in the DA mode has been observed in high entropy alloy (HEA) fatigue tests (Suzuki *et al.* [6]). The proposed model suggests that a faceted secondary crack, induced by cyclic loading, coalescences with the main crack, serving as a mechanism for propagation.

The concept of DA mode fatigue crack propagation extends to areas experiencing high plastic deformation during shearing (Zhang *et al.* [7]) or in carbon steel subjected to mixed-mode loading (Chen *et al.* [8]). In each instance, damage is attributed to shear strain localization resulting from activating a specific slip system in the crystal ahead of the crack. Hamada *et al.* [9] propose that the localized shear strain region termed a “unit,” serves as the primary site for damage-accumulating fatigue crack growth. This unit’s characteristics are highly contingent on the crystalline structure, exhibiting considerable size and shear strain value variability. The fatigue crack propagation behaviour in the damage accumulation mode is marked by significant variability and remains unpredictable. This variability is ascribed to the diverse nature of the units. The attainment of predictability would be instrumental in accurately forecasting the fatigue limit of high-strength steels.

Hamada *et al.* [9] conducted cyclic pure Mode II loading tests on cold-rolled SUS430 steel with a texture, aiming to establish a correlation between shear plastic strain distribution under unloading and crack propagation behaviour. The study revealed a connection between shear plastic strain and crack propagation rate. However, in the experiments by Hamada *et al.*, the plastic strain under load couldn’t be directly measured due to limitations in the test method. Consequently, they analyzed the correlation between plastic strain under unloading and crack propagation rate. It’s essential to emphasize that the plastic strain under load, a crucial factor for predicting fatigue crack growth behaviour, is an estimated value. As DA mode fatigue cracks propagate through repeated crack initiation, the range of shear plastic strain ($\Delta\gamma_{xy}$) becomes a pivotal parameter for prediction (Briffod *et al.* [10]). Therefore, measuring shear plastic strain under load is imperative.

This study observed shear plastic strain distribution under both loaded and unloaded conditions for the cold-rolled SUS430 steel specimen, maintaining the same microstructure as in Hamada *et al.* [9]. The correlation between the crystalline structure and strain distribution was analyzed to discuss material factors influencing strain localization. The Digital Image Correlation (DIC) method was employed to measure shear plastic strain distribution.

This study defines “strain localization” as a plastic strain distribution deviating from the expected range based on continuum mechanics influenced by the material crystalline structure and cyclic loading. According to continuum mechanics, the plastic zone typically exhibits a symmetrical shape for the crack. However, the distribution of localized plastic strain is observed to be asymmetrical or concentrated in a narrower region.

EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

Specimen

The test material comprises two ferritic stainless steel SUS430 variants manufactured through different processes. One variant is a thin film produced via cold rolling by Niraco Corporation, Japan. This material exhibits a microstructure resulting from the rolling process, making it prone to DA mode fatigue crack propagation. While the surface microstructure is influenced by rolling, it does not significantly impact crack propagation behaviour due to a multi-layered microstructure in the thickness direction.

The second material is a 3 mm thick plate of SUS430 from Niraco Corporation, Japan. This plate was sliced perpendicular to the rolling direction using wire electrical discharge machining and then polished to a thickness of 30 μm to obtain a thin film. The microstructure of the sliced material, thinned by this method, is almost unaffected by rolling. This material consists of one or two crystal grains in the thickness direction. It is well-suited for studying the correlation between strain distribution on the material surface and the crystalline structure.

This study distinguishes two types of thin films produced by different methods: α , produced by cold rolling, and β , produced by slicing the plate. Due to its body-centered cubic structure, SUS430 is susceptible to damage accumulation type fatigue crack propagation, attributed to its numerous slip systems.

The preparation of both thin films involved the same methods, followed by punching into 3 mm diameter discs and polishing. Fatigue cracks were induced by introducing notches using a focused ion beam (FIB system: FEI Quanta 200 3D). In the α film, notches 600 μm long were introduced parallel to the rolling direction, whereas in the β film, notches 400 μm long were introduced.

Following creating a 400 μm notch in the β film, the crystal orientation in front of the crack tip was analyzed using EBSD to identify a grain with a Taylor factor, indicating its susceptibility to plastic deformation under shear load. Subsequently, the notch was extended from the front side of the observation surface to position the identified grain at the crack tip using FIB machining. Despite the smaller radius of the notch compared to the back side, precise positioning of the notch tip on the targeted grain was achievable. Upon introducing the notches, the specimen surface was randomly patterned with colloidal silica to measure shear plastic strain using the DIC method described below. Figure 1 illustrates the specimen's geometry, and Figure 2 provides an SEM image of the FIB-notch tip.

FIGURE 1 Shapes and dimensions of the specimen (unit: μm).

FIGURE 2 Example of FIB notch tip.

Fatigue test and measurement methods

The specimens in this study underwent cyclic pure Mode II loading, involving two types of tests: stress ratio: $R = 0$ and $R = -1$ tests. The loading stress intensity factor range was $\Delta K_{II} = 5 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$ for the $R = 0$ test (test 1) and $\Delta K_{II} = 10 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$ for the $R = -1$ test (test 2). In test (1), positive shear stress was applied for 0.5 cycles and unloaded for one cycle. Test (2) applied positive shear stress at 0.25 cycles, unloaded at 0.5 cycles, and negative shear stress at 0.75 cycles, followed by unloading at one cycle. Both tests utilized a triangular waveform for the shear stress loading.

The tests were conducted in the Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) for continuous in-situ observation under loaded conditions. A general-purpose compact fatigue testing machine (DEBEN MT5000) was employed. A novel fixture was developed in this study to apply shear stress in the tensile and compression fatigue testing machine, integrated with the fatigue testing machine for cyclic Mode II loading tests on the specimens. Figure 3 illustrates a schematic diagram of the test setup. Kyowa Dengyo's instant adhesive CC-36 was used to bond the specimen and test the fixture. This test applied shear and bending stress to the entire specimen, unlike Hamada *et al.* [4], which was characterized by pure Mode II loading.

Observation of plastic strain in front of the crack tip was facilitated using the Digital Image Correlation (DIC) method. SEM images were captured at specified load cycles, and the VID-2D software from Correlated Solutions was employed for surface analysis.

FIGURE 3 Schematic diagram of the fatigue experiment.

Microstructure observation

This study conducted microstructural observations on specimen β using the Electron Backscatter Diffraction (EBSD) method to explore the relationship between microstructure and plastic strain. The analysis was carried out utilizing a Hitachi High-Technologies SU6600 scanning electron microscope. Additionally, the study introduced the Taylor factor for shear loading. In polycrystals, plastic deformation occurs through shear deformation caused by the glides of dislocations on the slip planes of crystals. This implies that the critical stress at which plastic deformation occurs is not the yield strength σ_Y but the critical resolved shear stress τ^{CRSS} acting in the slip plane. The Taylor factor can be employed to express the yield stress.

$$\sigma_Y = M\tau^{CRSS} \tag{1}$$

The Taylor factor, denoted by M , serves as a relative index of resistance to deformation, where a smaller value of M indicates easier deformation. To obtain the Taylor factor for shear loading, the shear stress can be converted to normal stress acting in the 45-degree direction using equation (2), which states that two times the shear stress, τ , is equal to the normal stress, σ .

$$2\tau = \sigma \tag{2}$$

Therefore, the shear load Taylor factor, M_τ , can be established by measuring and calculating the Taylor factor, M , under tensile load and subsequently halving that value.

$$2M_\tau = M \tag{3}$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Figure 4 exhibits SEM images depicting the fatigue test results for the cold-rolled steel at different load cycles ($N = 0, 0.5, 10, 20,$ and 200 cycles) (Hamada and Ookawa [11]). Notably, the sub-crack initiates at $N = 10$ and becomes visible at $N = 20$. By $N = 20$, the propagating crack length reaches approximately $1.6 \mu\text{m}$, while at $N = 200$, it extends to around $4.6 \mu\text{m}$.

Figure 5 illustrates the shear plastic strain distribution, measured using the DIC method, with the displayed strain range set from -7% to 7% [11]. Shear strain localizes in front of the notch under shear load, decreasing with unloading. However, the maximum strain value increases with cyclic loading. The region where shear strain is localized corresponds to the area where fatigue crack propagation occurs. The shear strain value is higher closer to the notch tip, gradually decreasing away from it. Examination of shear strain under load reveals that shear plastic strain localizes to a narrower region as the number of cycles increases. Regions of large strain, scattered in the vicinity of the notch after $N = 50$, are attributed to noise in the measurement caused by fatigue crack propagation and are distinct from strain.

These results indicate the necessity of introducing a new element into the prediction method for previously presented damage accumulation mode fatigue crack propagation behaviour [9]. The specific prediction method is illustrated in Fig. 6, where the red dashed line represents the prediction method, and the black line shows the construction of the evaluation method.

FIGURE 4 Fatigue crack propagation behaviour for cold rolled SUS430 [11].

FIGURE 5 Shear strain evolution for cold rolled SUS430 under pure cyclic Mode II loading [11].

The behaviour of each element is expressed in terms of continuum behaviour and real material behaviour. While the latter is observable, it is insufficient for accurate prediction. To address this issue, mesoscopic behaviour is introduced between macroscopic and microscopic behaviour. The average continuum strain is derived from the strength mechanism of the real material, based on the external force applied to it. The properties of the material at the crack tip are then extracted and coarse-grained to predict the fatigue life of the real material, taking into account the effects of the microstructure. Additionally, the need to predict and account for strain localization due to cyclic loading has been identified, with addressing the treatment of cyclic strain localization being a future task.

FIGURE 6 Damage accumulation mode fatigue crack propagation evaluation strategy [9].

CONCLUSIONS

This study introduced a novel in-situ observation test method, focusing on the fatigue crack extension mode. Cyclic pure Mode II fatigue tests were conducted under loading and unloading conditions on cold-rolled SUS430 with a specific microstructure. Observations of shear plastic strain distributions were conducted under both loaded and unloaded conditions, with subsequent analysis of the correlation between crystalline structure and strain distribution. The experimental results showed that both the proposed strain localization and cyclic strain localization should be considered.

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